

DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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On June 16 this year at a video conference chaired by the President on the priorities of the higher education system, the training of young people as specialists with world-class knowledge and skills, the continuous development of higher education, the inclusion of professors in the higher education system drew particular attention to the need to improve it. After all, in recent years a number of measures aimed at the innovative development of economic and social spheres in the country, all-round **support for science and research**, modernization of higher education and the development of high moral, intellectual and moral qualities have been taken.

I. On improving the legal and regulatory framework of the higher education system on the initiative of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, the legal and regulatory framework of the higher education system has been improved to ensure the quality and efficiency of research and innovation. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, **21 Resolutions of the President** and **29 Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers** were adopted.

In implementing these documents, the main objective of the **Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan** for 2019-2021 is to develop human capital, stimulate science and scientific activity, expand the scale of innovation, finance innovation, venture capital and venture financing. Main funding The Concept of science development has been approved and the strategy of integrated development of scientific activity in our country has been approved.

II. As a result of reforms in higher education, the number of higher education institutions in the country has reached 140 in recent years, and today there are 4,585 employees, 312 vice-rectors, 537 deans, 2,129 heads of departments and 1,607 heads. of departments. There are also branches of 24 foreign higher education institutions. Since 2020, in accordance with the

"Classification of Higher Professional Education Specialties and Master Degrees" there will be 267 undergraduate and 561 graduate degrees in 6 areas of education, 25 fields of study on the basis of state educational standards. The share of foreign branches of HEI and non-state HEI this year also increased significantly - 212 areas of training and 27 specialties.

In recent years, 95 bachelor's and 79 master's degree programs have been implemented at 58 institutions of higher education in cooperation with foreign institutions of higher education.

Since the academic year 2021/2022 the International Standard Classification of Education (2011) is introduced in the system of higher education. At the same time, in accordance with the requirements of international standards, training will be carried out in 11 disciplines, 29 fields of education and specialties. In this regard, the main goal is to create a new generation of curricula, the introduction of multilevel bachelor's and master's degree programs to ensure academic mobility.

Currently, the contingent of students in higher education is 692,611 people, 461,242 people - bachelor (full-time), 134,756 people - part-time, 15,319 people - special part-time, 16,261 people - evening school, 2565 people - secondary special education. 22 332 people in the specialty (part-time), 10218 people in joint educational program, 28,990 master's students and 928 master's students in the joint master's program. 4,285 of them are international students.

**MODERN EDUCATIONAL LABORATORY
KITS INDICATORS OF SUPPLY WITH**

Youth attendance increased from 9% to 25% compared to 2017, 73% of academic high school graduates earned a college degree in the 2020/2021 school year, and the number of scholarships for girls from low-income families doubled. to 2,000.

III. As a result of the work done to increase scientific potential in the system of higher education, the scientific potential was increased by 1.2 times compared to 2017, and this year the percentage of higher education institutions in the country reached 38%.

As a result of reforms in postgraduate research training, the quota for admission to doctoral and postdoctoral programs has quadrupled.

In order to meet the needs of scientific and pedagogical staff at the stage of targeted doctoral and doctoral studies in higher

education institutions a research institute of interns was created, the number of doctoral students has increased by 3.9 times.

This year the number of academic councils increased by 57% compared to 2017, and the number of academic councils for awarding academic degrees in higher education institutions of the republic reached 84. Over the past three years, 1,693 professors and teachers have defended doctoral dissertations, and the number of teachers with degrees in higher education has reached 9,636. The nation's higher education research capacity of 2,230 doctoral candidates and 7,506 doctoral candidates increased by 5.1 percent compared to 2017. The average age of graduates is 49 years (PhD - 56, PhD - 43), the proportion of retired doctors is 45%.

IV. In order to improve the scientific work of higher educational institutions, the number of articles published in the journals of the scientific and technical database Scopus has doubled to 2,563.

Portal "Scientific journals of Uzbekistan" was created on the basis of the Digital Commons platform (Bepress) together with the Dutch company "Elsevier", which hosts 41 scientific journals of higher

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL DATA
SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES PUBLISHED IN THE DATABASE

educational institutions in Uzbekistan and is adapted to international standards. Their citation rate was 125,812 in 108 countries, and the number of professors and lecturers with a Hirsch index above 3 was 362.

V. International ranking and increasing the efficiency of innovation activities 4 higher educational institutions registered 351-400 places in the QS ranking.

In order to ensure the integration of education and production in higher education institutions and attract specialists to training, 1125 scientific events were organized. Within the framework of these activities were received 1262 scientific developments, 959 patents, certificates of certification of products and inventions.

At present, the total value of scientific and technical recommendations on scientific activities of higher educational institutions is 140.4 billion soums. 231 projects are being implemented to the amount of soums.

The number of patents for inventions received by higher educational institutions was 54, for useful models - 46, for industrial designs - 8, for educational products - 1871.

In recent years we have introduced a system of rewarding 30% to 60% of professors, teachers and research staff with doctoral and master's degrees at a cost of 11 billion soums. The sums were channeled to higher education institutions.

A special electronic platform was developed to effectively coordinate the system of additional payments to employees with academic degrees, to ensure transparency in the process and to correctly and promptly form an order for state budget funding.

VII. In the area of providing institutions of higher education with modern textbooks, the Textbook Coordination Council for Higher Education

educational and scientific literature

published 1,306 titles in 2018 (463 titles and 843 textbooks), in 2019. - 1,980 titles (1,299, 2,099) and 2 (731 titles). In 2021, 718 titles (826 titles and 1,892 textbooks) and 1,438 textbooks (393 titles and 1,045 textbooks) were published and distributed.

- In order to improve the provision of higher educational institutions with training and laboratory equipment more than 260 training and laboratory sets were purchased in more than 100 higher educational institutions at the expense of budgetary funds and extra-budgetary funds of higher educational institutions.

- On the basis of the above-mentioned and based on the analysis of ongoing reforms in Uzbekistan in the sphere of science and innovations, we believe that special attention should be paid to the following tasks

- short-term improvement of scientific competence, for this purpose to establish the procedure for awarding academic degrees in relevant specialties in higher educational institutions and the system of recognition of academic degrees awarded by other higher educational institutions;

- Granting the right to independently determine the order of creation of textbooks and teaching aids, as well as textbooks to improve the teaching and methodological support of specialized disciplines in the transition to the credit-module of the university;

- Full commissioning of teaching and laboratory equipment purchased at the expense of the state budget of higher educational institutions of the republic, extra-budgetary funds, loans and grants from foreign donor organizations.

- Organization of scientific activities of universities based on the prospects of socio-economic development of the regions, forecasting of innovative development on the basis of analysis;

- Research and systematization of mechanisms ensuring that higher education institutions take a worthy place in international rankings;

- Implementation of advanced foreign system of credit assessment based on modular training, analysis of the educational process in higher education institutions based on the credit-module system, revision of the content of the subjects taught, higher education in professions requiring higher education;

- it is important for graduates of state and non-state institutions of higher education to create a healthy competitive environment based on the same in-demand industry skills based on labor market conditions.

INNOVATIVE
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